

Assessment of Different Image Fusion Techniques Used for Multi-Sensor Optical and SAR Data

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ABSTRACT

In this study a detailed assessment of various image fusion techniques is performed to provide a fair opportunity to the researchers in selecting an appropriate image fusion technique for their specific requirement. Total 10-pixel level image fusion techniques starting with 7 conventional strategies namely, Averaging, Brovey Transform, Multiplicative, High Pass Filter (HPF), High Pass Modulation (HPM), IHS and Principal Component Analysis(PCA) followed by 3 hybrid techniques namely, IHS-BT, PCA-HPF and Min-Max methods are included in this study. A detailed in-depth assessment of all these 10 image fusion techniques was performed to highlight their relative advantage and limitation along with their performance based upon the visual and statistical analysis.

Keywords: Image fusion, SAR, multispectral data, Image processing.

I. INTRODUCTION

Availability of multi-sensor satellites operating in different portions of the electromagnetic spectrum like optical, microwave, thermal etc. has provided huge opportunity to application scientists to exploit the unique potential of different sensors for various remote sensing applications. However, it has been observed that for most of the applications, multi-sensor remote sensing data provide much more information as compared to satellite data from single source. It can be achieved by either combining the separately extracted/retrieved information using remote sensing data from different satellites or by using fused product generated from multi-sensor remote sensing data. Out of the two approaches, image fusion approach is more useful and straight-forward. Therefore, image fusion of multi-sensor satellite images is an important component of digital image processing. Image fusion is the process of combining two or more images to form a new image in such a way that it not only highlights the relevant information but also preserves the features of source images [1, 2].

Remote Sensing and Image Fusion is an increasingly important research area. The fused image generated in this process holds significantly more information than the input images, making it more suitable for various computer processing tasks such as data analysis, classification, target area recognition, pattern and condition understanding, and other monitoring activities. The primary goal of image

fusion is to minimize redundancy and maximize relevant information from a given set of images, thereby enhancing the accuracy of image interpretation and analysis [3, 4].

Fused images provides insights that are not possible to obtain from individual datasets alone which further leads to more informed decision making and improved outcomes. SAR and optical satellite data provides complementary information about an object. SAR data is generated based on the backscatter characteristics of the target and is sensitive towards physical, geometrical and dielectrical properties of the target. Due to unique interaction of Radar signal with the target, it can differentiate between smooth and rough surfaces and is sensitive toward the shape, size, structure, orientation and water content of the target. Whereas multi-spectral FCC image can highlight features that have unique reflectance properties in various bands covered by visible and IR region of the electromagnetic spectrum. This composite is particularly effective in vegetation analysis, as healthy vegetation reflects large portion of near-infrared (NIR) and absorbs large portion of Red light. Therefore, in standard FCC, vegetation appears in vibrant red colour. FCC can enhance the detection of water bodies, as they absorb more NIR light and thus appear darker, providing a clear contrast against the surrounding land [5].

Combination of remote sensing data acquired by different satellites operating in different portions of electromagnetic spectrum provides many advantages such as complementary data utilisation, feature enhancement, Improvement in Image Classification, better change detection, substitution of missing data from one satellite, replacing defected data and many others. There are three different processing levels in Image fusion which are

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classified according to the stage at which the fusion takes place as shown in Fig. 1. The three levels are pixel level, feature level and the decision level [6].

In spite of the fact that there are many image fusion techniques already available to fuse multi-sensor remote sensing data sets, image fusion techniques are continuously evolving with time. Out of many available techniques, Image fusion techniques can be broadly classified in the following seven categories [7 - 10]:

- (1) Classical methods (e.g. Averaging method)
- (2) Statistical methods (e.g. BT method)
- (3) Transform Based methods (e.g. Wavelet method)
- (4) Deep Learning methods (e.g. GAN method)
- (5) Numerical methods (e.g. Multiplicative method)
- (6) Component Substitution methods (e.g. HIS method)
- (7) Hybrid Fusion Techniques (e.g. Wavelet-HIS method)

Fig. 1. Image Fusion Levels

II. DATASET AND STUDY AREA

The study area was selected as parts of Agra, Mathura (U.P.) and Bharatpur (Rajasthan) districts. This study area was chosen as it covers large number of land cover classes like human settlement (cities, towns, villages), wasteland (gullied/ravine, scrub land, barren land, salt affected land), river, wetland, aquatic vegetation, grassland, varying forest cover (dense, sparse, open), irrigated agricultural land, rain fed agricultural land etc. Multi spectral optical data from ‘Harmonized Sentinel-2 MSI: Multi Spectral Instrument, Level-1C’ as shown in Fig. 2 & SAR data from ‘Sentinel-1 SAR GRD: C-band Synthetic Aperture Radar Ground Range Detected - Log scaling’ as shown in Fig. 3, were used in the study.

III. METHODOLOGY

Google Earth Engine (GEE) was used to retrieve the remote sensing multi-sensor data and also to perform various [11]. The dataset included the pictures from the month of March 2022. It had 14,486 images of that region over the time from Sentinel-1 and 1,17,477 images of that region from Sentinel-2. The median composite of the images in that particular data was computed to form a

single image and used for analysis. It matches the band by their names and stacks the matching bands and then calculates the median value hence effectively reducing the image collection.

Since multi-sensor SAR data and multi-spectral optical data used in the study had same spatial resolution of 10meterseach, it is clear that image fusion in the study is not going to improve the spatial resolution. However, study clearly indicated that the fused images generated using 10 different image fusion techniques, offers several advantages, which we are going to discuss in the results and discussions section.

Sentinel-1 SAR provides radar data, which is highly effective for all-weather, day-and-night observations and excels in detecting surface roughness, moisture and structural changes. Whereas Sentinel-2 offers high-resolution optical imagery, which is known for capturing detailed information on land cover, vegetation health, and surface reflectance under clear weather conditions. Optical images face obstruction due to clouds whereas SAR images are available irrespective of weather and sunlight conditions due to its penetration capability and active sensor mode. Additionally, urban planning benefits from the fusion, as Radar’s sensitivity to man-made structures and optical data’s high spectral resolution provide a more detailed and accurate representation of urban areas. Moreover, it helps in better distinction of crops and forest cover as SAR data is sensitive texture, volume, canopy moisture, structure, and underneath soil moisture/soil roughness. Sentinel-2’s optical imagery provides crucial information for identifying newly sown fields, as freshly planted areas reflect light differently compared to mature crops or bare soil [12, 13]

Fig. 2. Sentinel-1 Image(C-Band)

Fig. 3. Sentinel-2 FCC Image (Bands: B8, B4, B3)

PRE PROCESSING:

Firstly, both the images were set to same coordinate space. As both the images had same resolution so resampling step was skipped. SAR data was noisy and hence an enhanced lee filter was used for speckle filtering. The images were filtered to get the VV polarisation which is generally used for land cover identification using SAR images. Cross-polarised VH image was not selected as it has enhanced sensitivity towards vegetation compared to other land cover classes. The pixel values with intensity less than -30dB were masked to reduce noise. The Sentinel-2 data was first filtered with the images having less than 20% cloud cover then 'QA60' band was used and the bits for cirrus and other small clouds were reset to mask it. These operations ensured a cloud free multispectral remote sensing data for further analysis. Both the multi-sensor Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 images were then converted to a scale of 0 to 1 so that both the image pixel values are in same scale. Once multi-sensor SAR and multi-spectral images are ready, both these images were fused with the help of 10 different image fusion techniques as described in next section [14, 15]

IV. IMAGE FUSION TECHNIQUES CONSIDERED FOR DETAILED ASSESSMENT

A. AVERAGING METHOD

The averaging technique is a straight-forward and commonly used method in image fusion in the context of combining optical and SAR imagery. This technique involves taking the pixel-by-pixel average of the input images to produce a fused image. By averaging the pixel values as shown in Fig. 4 and defined by eq. 1. This method is not only simple, but also effectively reduces noise and highlights the common features present in both images.

$$DN_{fused} = \frac{DN_{fcc} + DN_{sar}}{2} \tag{1}$$

Fig. 4. Flowchart showing the working of Averaging Method

B. MULTIPLICATIVE METHOD

The multiplicative technique in image fusion shown in Fig. 5 is a straight-forward method that involves multiplying the pixel values of the input images resulting in a fused image (eq. 2). This technique is particularly

effective when combining images that capture different but complementary types of information. This technique may lead to pixel value saturation, where the resulting values exceed the maximum representable range, necessitating post-processing adjustments which includes bringing the new pixel values back to original scale by linear stretching so that saturation can be avoided.

$$DN_{fused} = DN_{fcc} * DN_{sar} \tag{2}$$

Fig. 5. Flowchart showing the working of Multiplicative Method

C. BT METHOD

The Brovey Transform method involves a mathematical combination of multi-spectral and panchromatic bands as shown in Fig. 6. In this method, each multispectral band is multiplied by the ratio of the panchromatic band to the sum of all multispectral bands (eq. 3 to eq. 5). The result is a fused image that preserves the color information of the multi-spectral data while significantly enhancing its spatial resolution.

$$R_{new} = PAN * \frac{R_{fcc}}{R_{fcc} + G_{fcc} + B_{fcc}} \tag{3}$$

$$G_{new} = PAN * \frac{G_{fcc}}{R_{fcc} + G_{fcc} + B_{fcc}} \tag{4}$$

$$B_{new} = PAN * \frac{B_{fcc}}{R_{fcc} + G_{fcc} + B_{fcc}} \tag{5}$$

Fig. 6. Flowchart showing the working of BT Method

D. HPF METHOD

The high-pass filter technique is a method employed in image fusion (Fig. 7). This technique works by extracting the high-frequency component details and edges from the panchromatic image using a high-pass filter defined by eq. 6. This technique accentuates variations in pixel intensity associated with fine features. These high-frequency

components are then combined with the corresponding low-frequency components containing color and spectral information from the multispectral image to create a fused image.

$$DN_{fused} = DN_{fcc} + (DN_{sar} - DN_{LPF}(sar)) \quad (6)$$

Fig. 7. Flowchart showing the working of HPF Method

E. HPM METHOD

The high-pass modulation technique is a method employed in image fusion. The process involves applying a high pass filter to the panchromatic image to extract high frequency components as shown in Fig. 8 and can be performed using eq. 7. It contains detailed spatial information such as edges and fine textures. These high frequency details are then modulated and combined with the low resolution multispectral images, resulting in a fused image that maintains the original spectral characteristics while significantly improving spatial details. The modulation is controlled by a modulation parameter K and it separates this method from HPF.

$$DN_{fused} = DN_{fcc} + K * (DN_{sar} - DN_{LPF}(sar)) \quad (7)$$

where

$$K = \frac{DN_{fcc}}{DN_{LPF}(sar)}$$

Fig. 8. Flowchart showing the working of HPM Method

F. IHS METHOD

RGB bands are transformed to IHS, where I stand for intensity, which represents the brightness or lightness of the color, capturing the grayscale information of the image. H stands for Hue, which tells about the average or dominant wavelength of light that is contributing to the color. S stands for saturation, which represents the purity or vividness of the color, indicating how much the color is diluted with white light color space. This technique (Fig. 9) may be performed using eq. 8 to eq. 11

$$\begin{pmatrix} I \\ V_1 \\ V_2 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{3} & \frac{1}{3} & \frac{1}{3} \\ \frac{1}{\sqrt{6}} & \frac{1}{\sqrt{6}} & -\frac{2}{\sqrt{6}} \\ \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} & -\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} R \\ G \\ B \end{pmatrix} \quad (8)$$

Also,

$$H = \tan^{-1}\left(\frac{V_2}{V_1}\right) \quad (9)$$

and

$$S = \sqrt{V_1^2 + V_2^2} \quad (10)$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} R \\ G \\ B \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{3} & \frac{1}{\sqrt{6}} & \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \\ \frac{1}{3} & \frac{1}{\sqrt{6}} & -\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \\ \frac{1}{3} & -\frac{2}{\sqrt{6}} & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} I \\ V_1 \\ V_2 \end{pmatrix} \quad (11)$$

Fig. 9. Flowchart showing the working of IHS Method

G. PCA METHOD

It aims at reducing the dimensionality of multivariate data while retaining relevant information as possible. It converts a correlated dataset into an uncorrelated one, thereby reducing redundancy in the image data. The process involves transforming the multispectral data using PCA, calculating the eigenvalues and eigenvectors of the correlation matrix between the bands of the multi-spectral image to obtain the principal components as shown in Fig. 10. PC1 of the multi-spectral image is replaced with the matched panchromatic image to create a new first principal component PC1'. This new component, is stacked back with the other principal components, undergo inverse PCA transformation to produce the fused image.

Fig. 10. Flowchart showing the working of PCA Method

H. MIN-MAX METHOD

Min-Max hybrid fusion shown by Fig. 11 is an image fusion technique that combines the strengths of both the minimum and maximum value selection methods to enhance the quality and interpretability of the fused image. In this approach, the pixel values from multiple input images are compared as defined by eq. 12 to eq. 14. This hybrid method effectively captures the most relevant

features from each source image, ensuring that both bright and dark regions are accurately represented.

$$DN_{fused} = \frac{DN_{min} + DN_{max}}{2} \quad (12)$$

where

$$DN_{min} = \text{Min}(DN_{fcc}, DN_{sar}) [11, 12] \quad (13)$$

and

$$DN_{max} = \text{Max}(DN_{fcc}, DN_{sar}) [11, 12] \quad (14)$$

Fig. 11. Flowchart showing the working of Min-Max Method

I. IHS-BT METHOD

By combining two well-known algorithms, IHS and BT, the IHS-BT method enables parameter adjustments to represent a hybrid IHS-BT fusion (Fig. 12). This approach addresses the spectral distortion issues associated with IHS and BT as it balances saturation using a parameter to control the degree of saturation stretch (BT) and compression (IHS). The IHS method performs optimally with nonlinear equations whereas the BT method achieves minimal distortions, using linear equations, particularly for saturation values defined by eq. 15 and eq. 16.

$$\begin{pmatrix} R'_{IHS-BT} \\ G'_{IHS-BT} \\ B'_{IHS-BT} \end{pmatrix} = \alpha \begin{pmatrix} R + K * (PAN - I) \\ G + K * (PAN - I) \\ B + K * (PAN - I) \end{pmatrix} \quad (15)$$

where

$$\alpha = \frac{PAN}{I + K * (PAN - I)} \quad (16)$$

Fig. 12. Flowchart showing the working of IHS-BT Method

J. PCA-HPF METHOD

To improve performance, PCA and HPF fusion methods are integrated as shown in Fig. 13. This method starts by transforming a multi-spectral image using PCA. Also, a Gaussian filter is used to smoothen the panchromatic image. The difference between the

panchromatic and the smoothed image is obtained to get the high spatial detail of the panchromatic image. This detail is then combined into the PC1 using a gain parameter K. The new first principal component stacked with the other calculated components are transformed back using inverse PCA to create the fused multi-spectral image (eq. 17).

$$DN_{PC1'} = DN_{PC1} + K * (DN_{sar} - DN_{LPPF}(sar)) \quad (17)$$

where

$$K = \frac{SD_{PC1}}{SD_{sar}}$$

Fig. 13. Flowchart showing the working of PCA-HPF Method

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

By adopting the detailed procedure described in the previous section, all the 10 image fusion techniques (i.e. Averaging Method, Multiplicative Method, BT Method, HPF Method, HPM Method, IHS Method, PCA Method, Min-Max Method, IHS-BT Method and PCA-HPF Method) were applied on Sentinel-1 SAR and Sentinel-2 Multi-spectral images one-by-one to generate 10 fused images. All the fused images are shown in Fig. 14 to Fig. 23. In order to provide the readers a fair opportunity to realise and to observe the improvement due to fusion of multi-sensor images, Sentinel-1 SAR and Sentinel-2 multi-spectral images are also included in all the 10 figures (from Fig. 14 to Fig. 23).

All the fused images generated using 10 different image fusion techniques were compared with their parent images acquired from Sentinel-1 SAR and Sentinel-2 multi-spectral sensors based upon two broad approaches. Firstly, based upon the detailed visual interpretation and secondly on the basis of statistical analysis. It is required to emphasize the importance of careful visual observation of all the fused images as statistical analysis alone may lead to misleading conclusion. Details of visual and statistical review of all the 10 image fusion techniques using 10 fused images shown in Fig. 14 to Fig. 23 are provided below:

Visual Review: Visual review of quality of fused images was based on the three broad land cover features i.e. settlements, vegetation and water bodies. This exercise was done carefully by inspecting the enhancement in separability and increase in contrast for the three major land cover classes i.e. settlements, vegetation and water bodies. Followed by looking out for any missing data or improper blending like improper pixel values for settlement, water bodies and vegetation. Outcome of visual

review of all the 10 image fusion techniques based upon visual interpretation of fused image, original image and 11 topographic maps is shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Visual Review

Method	Settlements	Vegetation	Water Body
Averaging	Good	Average	Good
Multiplicative	Very Good	Average	Good
Brovey Transform	Very Good	Average	Good
High Pass Filter	Very Good	Average	Very Good
High Pass Modulation	Good	Good	Good
IHS - RGB	Good	Good	Poor
PCA	Poor	Good	Good
Min - Max	Average	Good	Good
IHS - BT	Good	Poor	Average
PCA - HPF	Average	Good	Good

Statistical Review: This review is based on the three statistical parameters and are compared with Sentinel-2 FCC image as the resultant fused image was a multi-band (coloured) image. Following statistical analysis were performed for all the ten fused images:

Bias of Mean (BOM): It is the difference between the means of the original image and the output image (fused) and normalized with respect to the mean of the original

image. The value zero shows that it is the same image. The negative value shows that the method has caused increase in the brightness of fused image whereas a positive value show that the resultant image is darker than original. Hence we need its value to be close to zero.

Correlation Coefficient (CC): It measures the correlation between the original and the output image (fused). The value 1 shows that it is the same image. 0 means the fused image has no relation with the original image and -1 shows that the fused image is completely inverted output of input image. Hence we need its value to be close to one.

Standard Deviation Difference (SDD): It is the difference between the standard deviations of the original colour image and the output image (fused). The value zero shows that it is the same image. The negative value shows that the method has caused increase in the contrast and variation in fused image whereas a positive value show that the resultant image has less contrast and variation than original. Hence we need its value to be close to zero.

In order to perform statistical analysis for the assessment of various image fusion techniques considered in this study, all the 10 fused output images shown in Fig. 14 to Fig. 23 were used to calculate BOM (Bias of Mean), CC (Correlation Coefficient) and SDD (Standard Deviation Difference). These operations were performed for all the three bands (i.e. Red, Green and Blue) of the fused image. Band wise values of BOM, CC and SDD for all the 10 image fusion techniques are summarised in Table 2.

Table 2. Standard Deviation Difference (SDD)

S. No.	Statistical Parameters	IMAGE FUSION TECHNIQUE									
		AVG	BT	HPF	HPM	IHS	MUL	PCA	IHS-BT	MIN-MAX	PCA-HPF
01	BOM - Red	0.246	0.182	0.001	0.002	0.325	0.378	0.115	0.510	-0.246	0.000
02	BOM - Green	0.036	0.193	0.001	0.004	0.312	0.376	0.213	0.436	-0.036	0.001
03	BOM - Blue	0.019	0.184	0.001	0.004	0.313	0.376	0.115	0.430	-0.019	0.001
04	BOM - Average	0.100	0.186	0.001	0.003	0.317	0.377	0.148	0.459	-0.100	0.001
05	CC - Red	0.757	0.752	0.877	0.785	0.689	0.491	0.999	0.650	0.757	0.917
06	CC - Green	0.618	0.637	0.713	0.695	0.677	0.595	0.920	0.654	0.718	0.818
07	CC - Blue	0.759	0.662	0.882	0.904	0.727	0.835	0.945	0.602	0.859	0.789
08	CC - Average	0.711	0.684	0.824	0.795	0.698	0.640	0.955	0.635	0.778	0.841
09	SDD - Red	0.027	-0.030	-0.007	0.045	-0.006	-0.020	0.000	0.000	-0.027	0.000
10	SDD - Green	0.031	-0.024	-0.005	0.024	0.001	-0.038	0.008	-0.005	-0.031	-0.005
11	SDD - Blue	0.015	-0.021	-0.011	0.017	0.022	-0.010	0.004	0.007	0.005	-0.002
12	SDD - Average	0.024	-0.025	-0.008	0.029	0.006	-0.023	0.004	0.001	-0.018	-0.002

Fig.14. Averaging Method

Fig. 17. High Pass Filter method

Fig.15. Multiplicative Method

Fig. 18. High Pass Modulation method

Fig. 16. Brovey Transform method

Fig. 19. IHS method

Fig. 20. Principal Component Analysis method

Fig. 22. IHS-BT method

Fig. 21. Min-Max method

Fig. 23. PCA-HPF method

Table 3. Analysis of all the methods

S. No.	Method	Advantages	Disadvantages	Visual Analysis	Statistical Analysis
1.	Averaging method	(a) It is simple and hence computationally easy and efficient. (b) Averages out random noises, causing smoother output fused image.	(a) It suppress important details and may also reduce contrast. (b) Leads to loss of sharpness in output fused images.	(a) Small urban settlements in fused image are better differentiable as compared with Sentinel-2 alone. (b) Better distinction of crops than in Sentinel-1 near U.P. - Rajasthan border.	(a) Positive BOM indicates less brightness (b) Pretty Good value of CC. (c) Positive SDD indicates less contrast.
2.	Multiplicative method	(a) It emphasizes those areas where both input images have high values.	(a) It can amplify noise present in the input images.	(a) Brighter settlement and crop areas with high intensities.	(a) Positive BOM indicates less brightness

S. No.	Method	Advantages	Disadvantages	Visual Analysis	Statistical Analysis
		(b) It is simple and hence computationally efficient technique.	(b) Multiplication of pixel values may lead to saturation as pixel values go out of range.	(b) Dull areas in the images caused more dullness in fused image causing difficulty in differentiation of features.	(b) Average value of CC (c) Negative SDD indicates more contrast.
3.	BT method	(a) Simple and intuitive image fusion technique capable of taking fractional portions into account. (b) It preserves the relative spectral contribution from all the input band.	(a) Areas with more brightness lose spatial quality as low fraction value. (b) Noise can majorly affect the fractional contribution.	(a) Settlements can be distinguished easily compared to previous two methods. (b) Areas with less variation in pixel values were less distinguishable after image fusion.	(a) Positive BOM indicates less brightness (b) Above average value of CC. (c) Negative SDD indicates more contrast.
4.	HPF method	(a) High percentage of the spectral characteristics from multi-spectral image are preserved in this method. (b) Enhances fine spatial details and edges by filtering out low-frequency components.	(a) Selection of high frequency components may also include noise. (b) Relatively complex. Depends on the kernel size of low pass filter.	(a) Even smaller settlements can be distinguished easily. (b) Better delineation of moist plants with water bodies	(a) Positive BOM indicates less brightness (b) High value of CC. (c) Negative SDD indicates more contrast.
5.	HPM method	(a) Minimize distortions as compared to HPF. (b) Provides more balanced integration by modulating high frequency components.	(a) Computationally intensive than other image fusion techniques discussed in this study (b) More complex as it depends on the kernel size and modulation parameter.	(a) Very small settlements are difficult to delineate (b) Less contrasting than HPF, which helps in effective focusing on crops as compared with settlements.	(a) Positive BOM indicates less brightness (b) Reasonably high value of CC. (c) Positive SDD indicates less contrast.
6.	IHS method	(a) By preserving Hue and Saturation, helps in preserving spectral information intact. (b) Easier to understand and to apply on multi-sensor images. (c) Popular amongst remote sensing researchers.	(a) This technique may introduce significant color distortion. (b) Highly saturated regions may not translate well, resulting in a loss of finer details.	(a) Good distinction of crops along with settlements. (b) May introduce spectral distortion.	(a) Positive BOM indicates less brightness (b) Above average value of CC. (c) Negative SDD indicates more contrast.
7.	PCA method	(a) Effectively reduces the dimensionality of the data. (b) Enhances significant features of image as	(a) Some information which is in the discarded components inevitably lost.	(a) Although, output fused image is highly matching with Sentinel-2, but	(a) Positive BOM indicates less brightness.

S. No.	Method	Advantages	Disadvantages	Visual Analysis	Statistical Analysis
		principal component is capable to capture most of the variance in the input images.	(b) Transforming to the principal components is computationally intensive and complex.	unable to highlight small settlements (b) Less spectral distortion in water bodies.	(b)Extremely high value of CC. (c) Positive SDD indicates less contrast.
8.	Min-Max method	(a) Effectively captures and enhances both bright and dark features. (b) Improves the overall contrast and dynamic range of the fused image.	(a) Computationally intensive due to processing of large dataset with high-resolution images. (b) This method overlooks intermediate pixel values that contain important subtle information.	(a) Small settlements can be identified along with bigger ones. (b) Finer details in areas with less variation are merged.	(a) Negative BOM indicates more brightness. (b) Pretty good value of CC. (c) Negative SDD indicates more contrast.
9.	IHS-BT method	(a) IHS ensures that color information should exist and should be accurate. (b) BT enhances spatial details. (c) K parameter controls image between IHS and BT methods.	(a) Computationally intensive as involves many transformation steps. (b) Optimal calculation of k depends on input images.	(a) Settlements are easier to be distinguished. (b) The output fused image loses its brightness, making it difficult for visual inspection.	(a) Positive BOM indicates less brightness. (b) Average value of CC. (c) Positive SDD indicates less contrast.
10.	PCA-HPF method	(a) PCA reduces dimensionality while HPF emphasizes high-frequency components. (b) Effectively reduces redundancy and highlights prominent features.	(a) Too much computation as both PCA and HPF requires high calculations. (b) As the output fused image consider only 3 components, it may lead to loss of data with less variations.	(a) Output fused Image seems like Sentinel-2 data leading to only large settlements properly visible. (b) Slight spectral distortion can be seen near water bodies.	(a) Positive BOM indicates less brightness. (b) High value of CC. (c) Negative SDD indicates more contrast.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

Availability of large variety of image datasets with diverse sensor parameters along with free access to satellite based remote sensing images through Google Earth Engine (GEE) have started new era of satellite remote sensing applications due to easy access to multi-temporal, multi-sensor, multi-frequency and multi-resolution data sets. Therefore, image data fusion has become a vital technique in remote sensing image analysis as it helps in facilitating the integration of the best features from variety of satellite based remote sensing datasets.

In this study a detailed assessment of advantage and shortcomings of various image fusion techniques have

been carried out on the basis of visual and statistical analysis. The visual analysis revealed following ranking for 10 image fusion techniques in descending order:

1. HPF
2. HPM
3. PCA-HPF
4. IHS
5. PCA
6. Min-Max
7. Multiplicative

8. BT
9. Averaging
10. IHS-BT.

whereas according to statistical analysis these methods were ranked as:

1. PCA-HPF
2. PCA
3. HPF
4. Min-Max
5. HPM
6. IHS
7. Averaging
8. IHS-BT
9. BT
10. Multiplicative.

It is interesting to note that ranking of ten pixel based image fusion techniques considered in this study are showing different rankings based upon the visual and statistical analysis. Therefore, it is more meaningful to combine the findings of two interpretation methods (viz. visual and statistical) to arrive at the best ranking of various image fusion techniques considered in this study. In order to arrive at a comprehensive ranking of image fusion techniques, both the rankings were combined to arrive at a more meaningful ranking of 10 image fusion technique (in descending order) given below:

1. HPF
2. PCA-HPF
3. HPM
4. PCA
5. Min-Max
6. IHS
7. Multiplicative
8. Averaging
9. BT
10. IHS-BT.

From this study, it is clear that although different image fusion techniques have their own advantage and shortcomings, it is necessary to make an unbiased assessment to suggest the researchers a fair ranking of popular image fusion techniques. It is expected that the ranking of 10 popular image fusion techniques resulted after a careful assessment, will be used by the researchers as a reference for multi-sensor image fusion.

Although, the results of this study are satisfactory, it should be noted that many other image fusion techniques

exist, which require transformation of image to other domain like Wavelet Transform, Curvelet Transform, Contourlet Transform etc. Moreover, ANN (Artificial Neural Networks), GAN (Generative Adversarial Networks) etc. can also be used for image fusion. However, these methods have not been evaluated in this study as the study was limited to the assessment of pixel based image fusion techniques to provide a fair ranking of popular image fusion techniques.

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